

RTBV was, however, detectable in TKM6, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and TN1 throughout the period after its detection. The results indicate that the virus

concentration in Utri Merah and Balimau Putih was reduced over time to below the level of detection and is the reason why past tests done at 3-4 WAI showed low

infection rates of RTBV. The results also suggest that Utri Merah and Balimau

Relationship between phenylalanine ammonialase (PAL) activity and blast (BI) resistance in rice

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We randomly selected seedlings of 30 rice cultivars at the three-leaf stage. They were surface-sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ for 5 min at room temperature, and then

Relationship between BI resistance scores and PAL activity in rice seedlings.

Cultivar	Score ^a	PAL activity (OD ₂₃₀ /g fresh wt per h)
Toride 1	0	0.435
Zhaiyeqing 8	1	0.429
Xiangzaoxian 1	1	0.416
IR52	2	0.423
IR62	3	0.431
Sanerai	3	0.423
Jinwan 1	3	0.421
Jinyou 1	3	0.417
Yangdao 2	3	0.416
IR29	3	0.389
Correlation coefficient		-0.4475 ns ^b
Teqing	4	0.420
Zhefu 802	4	0.404
IR58	4	0.400
Erjiufeng	4	0.393
Zaoxian 143	4	0.390
Lunhui 422	4	0.387
6188	4	0.372
M112	5	0.378
77-175	5	0.345
Jinxi 14	6	0.381
Hongyun 33	6	0.381
Jinza0 6	6	0.363
Erjiuai	6	0.346
73-07	6	0.342
Shenghong 16	7	0.374
22	7	0.359
Guichao 2	8	0.353
Menggudao	9	0.325
Hong 410	9	0.314
LJXTHG	9	0.309
Correlation coefficient		-0.8398*** ^c

^aBased on SES scale of 0-9. ^bNonsignificant at 5% probability level. ^cSignificant at 1% probability level.

rinsed five times in sterile distilled water. Leaves were cut off and crushed by hammering individually in boric acid buffer (pH 8.8), each liter supplemented with 0.5 g polyvinyl pyrrolidone. The mixture was centrifuged three times at 5,000 rpm for 25 min at 4 °C. Then 0.5 ml of the supernatant was mixed in a test tube with 3.5 ml of a reaction mixture that contained 20 mmo1 L-Phe 2 ml/liter and allowed to rest for 60 min at 30 °C. The absorbance of the mixture at 290 nm was recorded using a UV 120-02-01 model Ultraviolet-spectrophotometer

(Shimadzn Ltd. Co., Japan). The experiment was replicated four times.

The correlation coefficient was nonsignificant at 5% probability level for PAL activity and BI resistance in rice cultivars (*Standard evaluation system for rice* [SES] scores of 0-3) on the qualitative scale based on lesion type, but it was significant at 1% probability (scores of 4-9) on the quantitative scale based on the percentage of leaf area affected. This indicates that PAL activity increased as the BI resistance score decreased from 4 to 9 (see table). ■

Efficiency of natural selection for bacterial sheath rot (BSR) in bulked families

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BSR, induced by *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* Tanii, Miyajima, et Akita, was earlier reported on rice only in the northern part of Hokkaido, Japan. It was discovered in Burundi in 1982. This disease has since been identified in Madagascar and Latin America in rice, sorghum, maize, and wheat. In rice, BSR causes poor panicle exertion, leading to sterility of the nonexserted part of the panicle.

BSR is particularly damaging to modern varieties with the *sd1* gene and partially explains the poor performance of fixed varieties in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. We compared Ambalalava, a tall, fixed, variety that is well-adapted to BSR, with two F₃, F₆, F₇, and F₈ bulked populations from 1988 to 1991 at the same site at 1,550 m asl.

The two populations were grown at the site in 1987, but BSR pressure was very low. BSR incidence was measured as the percentage of partially exserted

panicles in a sample of 10 pots with three replications. Severity was estimated by the difference in weight between 25 sampled panicles with and without disease (mean of three replications).

Yield loss is measured by the incidence multiplied by severity of BSR.

1. BSR incidence in Burundi, 1988-91.

2. BSR severity in Burundi, 1988-91.

